

KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

Eagleton, C., Curtis, N., Economou, M., Oles, K., Waters, S. (2025), **Online Teaching and Learning with Digitised Collections**, [University Museums in Scotland](https://www.universitymuseums.org.uk/online-teaching-and-learning-with-digitised-collections), doi: [10.5281/zenodo.14850332](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14850332)

Collections

UMIS

Support and funding for the development and use of digital collections by a wide range of institutions – not just those that are already digitised and with a high profile.

Investigate more fully the technical and other issues affecting students' ability to access and use digitised collections, and to participate in collections-based learning online.

Commit to interoperability and sharing of resources, both through the use of standards such as IIIF, but also through more open licensing such as Creative Commons CC-BY that set the use of images for learning ahead of potential income generation.

Skills

Develop and deliver training for staff and students on how to find and use digitised museum and archive collections, as a complement to the information literacy programmes already offered.

Support digital skills development for staff and students and identify curriculum-based opportunities to apply these skills, broadening out the range of subjects to which teaching with collections is relevant.

Set new types of assignments to not only assess the skills and knowledge acquired by the students, but to also develop transferrable skills and employability.

Collaboration

Recognise and credit the contributions of collections and digitisation specialists to teaching and learning, and advocate for partnership-based approaches to working with academic staff.

Incentivise and support the development of innovative and collaborative practise through funding and recognition, including cross-departmental and cross-institutional skill-sharing and development opportunities.